

STRATEGIES OF TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: *Strategic planning of tourist areas in the development of international access and domestic tourism in Uzbekistan will ensure the sustainable development of the tourism industry. The creation of competitive tourism services in international tourism markets can be achieved through the joint efforts of interested countries, coordinated management institutions, effective use of the potential of the regions to promote it on the basis of a single Silk Road brand. The article reflects the work of one of the countries in Central Asia in 2022-2023 and in the framework of the CAREC-2030 strategy, as well as a SWOT analysis of the tourism region of Uzbekistan has been also done.*

Keywords: *Sustainable tourism, tourism strategy, tourism industry, Silk Road brand, CAREC countries.*

At the beginning of 2016, a process of radical reform of the tourism industry was launched in Uzbekistan. Transformations in the field of tourism were named as one of the strategic directions for the development of the national economy, which can ensure the accelerated development of regions.

The analysis showed a positive dynamic of growth in tourism. So, in 2016-2019, there was a significant increase in the number of foreign tourists visiting Uzbekistan. For comparison, if in 2016, 2 million foreign tourists visited the country, in 2019 their number increased 3.3 times and reached 6.7 million.

In 2018, the number of foreign tourists increased - by 98% compared to 2017, and the number of companies and organizations engaged in tourism activities - by 131%. It is notable that the growth in the number of tourists from different regions occurs in different ways. For example, the number of visitors from Central Asian countries increased by an average of 22-25% per year, while the annual growth among tourists from non-CIS countries was 50%.

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At the same time, positive results were noted in domestic tourism. Compared to 2016, the number of domestic tourists in 2019 almost doubled and amounted to 14.7 million.

It should be noted that due to the restrictions imposed against the backdrop of the coronavirus pandemic and the consequences of the global crisis, the tourism industry has suffered serious losses. In particular, the number of foreign tourists visiting Uzbekistan decreased by more than 4.5 times, to 1.5 million, and the volume of tourist services fell to \$261 million in 2020.

The government took comprehensive measures to increase the accommodation. Firstly, 22 types of requirements regulating the activities of hostels related to the type of budget housing have been canceled. In particular, the procedure for mandatory certification of hotel services provided by hostels has been canceled and the practice of working with a unified register of guest houses and hostels has been introduced. Secondly, in order to increase the number of small hotels, entrepreneurs were provided with 8 standard projects of small hotels up to 50 rooms free of charge and this measure is developed based on the experience of Turkey and South Korea.

As a result, the number of placements in the country has increased dramatically. In particular, from 2016 to 2020, their number increased from **750 to 1308** and the number of beds increased from **34,000 to 62,000**.

The CAREC Tourism Development Strategy 2030 is based on the vision of creating a “sustainable, safe, easily accessible, and well-known tourism region that offers a variety of unique year-round quality experiences to visitors along the Silk Road and distributes the benefits widely among its communities”.

The Silk Road is the most important route linking the major cities and tourist sites of the CAREC countries. In addition, the main national and transnational roads in the region are connected to the Great Silk Road, such as the Pamir Highway, the Karakoram Highway, the Genghis Khan Trail and the Trans-Siberian Railway.

CAREC tourism development vision and regional priority tourism clusters

The proposed concept of regional tourism under CAREC is based on the Silk Road as the most important tourism asset for the entire region and at the core of the overall regional tourism umbrella brand. It aims to maximize the international recognition of the Silk Road brand in order to further develop the tourism market segments mentioned in chapter III through the development of regional priority tourism clusters. According to the CAREC initiatives Uzbekistan tourism development strategy will be developed in those tourism types along the Silk road.

Heart of Central Asia: a 650 km route covering six countries - Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, the Kyrgyz Republic, Turkmenistan, Tajikistan and Afghanistan, focused on such tourism segments as cultural, adventure, urban and business tourism.

To realize the long-term vision, it is necessary to develop a strategic framework that builds on the main strengths of tourism in the Uzbekistan region, addresses its main weaknesses, reflects the main opportunities and is resilient to the main threats. Analysis of Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats (SWOT) is presented in Table 1:

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Table 1 - Analysis of Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats (SWOT)

Strengths	Weaknesses
<p>Pristine natural resources, unique tangible and intangible cultural heritage, and diversity across Uzbekistan region.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪Low population density even in metropolitan cities, making it a safe tourist destination. ▪Diversity and uniqueness of nomadic and sedentary cultures throughout the region, ethnic groups and religions. ▪Historic cities, heritage of ancient empires and UNESCO World Heritage Sites in the country. ▪Quality of accommodation and other tourist facilities in the capital and cities. ▪Unexplored destinations suitable for discovery. ▪Globally recognized common brand: Silk Road. ▪The local population is very welcoming to tourists. ▪Political location and government support for tourism development. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪High cost and poor air connectivity between CAREC capitals and distant markets. ▪Inadequate transportation infrastructure, roadside facilities on tourist routes, last mile access, tourist services and signage at tourist sites. ▪Cumbersome and time-consuming border crossing and visa procedures (including at airports). ▪Lack of brand awareness and image, resulting in a lack of knowledge of Uzbekistan and a poor perception of them as tourism destinations. ▪Limited capacity in social responsibility practices and conservation of tourist sites. ▪Limited multi-season experience in product development targeting the most attractive market segments. ▪Language barriers and lack of skilled workers, destination managers and guides.
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪Growing international interest and recognition of the Silk Road. ▪Continuous expansion of international tourism, especially to fast growing Asian markets, and travelers seeking new experiences and unusual destinations. ▪Major regional infrastructure projects being developed in the region. ▪The continued growth of information technology to enable potential travelers to collect information and interact digitally with potential service providers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪Growing global health risks and geopolitical conflicts with serious potential implications for the travel and tourism industry. ▪Climate change with global warming and environmental degradation. ▪Security and political instability in some border countries with Uzbekistan. ▪Economic downturn in major tourism markets. ▪Natural and man-made disasters.

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<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Tourism as an industry that can support economic recovery after the pandemic. ▪ Donor support for profitable tourism projects. 	
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Source: Designed by the author upon making scientific researches.

Based on a SWOT analysis, the CAREC 2030 Tourism Development Strategy identifies five key strategic frameworks for regional coverage where the implementation of regional initiatives and projects can help countries reap the social and economic benefits from sustainable tourism development (Figure 6). These include (i) air transport network maturity and infrastructure, (ii) quality and standards, (iii) skills development, (iv) marketing and branding, and (v) market intelligence. Cross-sectoral themes will be mainstreamed into all activities under the five strategic directions, including security, digital, gender, environmental sustainability, private sector participation and universal travel access. In addition, appropriate institutional and governance arrangements are needed to ensure effective implementation, monitoring, and evaluation of the CAREC Tourism Development Strategy 2030.

After making in-deep research in Tourism strategy Ireland 2012, we can offer 6 strategic areas which underpin these activities and support a continuous growth in visitors to Uzbekistan between 2022-2023.

<p>Targeting our best prospects</p>	<p>Tourism Uzbekistan will mainly focus on consumers that are interested in sight-seeing, pilgrimage and experiencing local culture. We will continue to review our best prospects next year to ensure we are targeting the right consumer. Marketing investment in 2022-2023 will be focused on our 10 key source markets - Kazakhstan, Tajikistan, Kyrgyzstan, Turkmenistan, Russia, Turkey, Afghanistan, China, South Korea, India, Germany, Japan, France, Italy.</p>
<p>Communicating a new brand positioning</p>	<p>A new positioning for the Tourism Uzbekistan Brand has been developed with a view to strengthening our competitive differentiation and increasing the vibrancy associated with a holiday here. The new positioning is focused on making us a more compelling holiday that consumers will want to visit now rather than someday in the future with motives based on Agritourism, sport tourism, pilgrimage & religious tourism, gastronomy tourism, adventure tourism, medical tourism, cultural & ethnic tourism.</p>
<p>Marketing to the consumer</p>	<p>A new suite of integrated, interactive and engaging communication has been designed for deployment around</p>

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	the world 2023. The new campaign will highlight Uzbekistan's distinctiveness through compelling communication to achieve maximum reach and impact in our target markets. Consumer will be able to access information and purchase the full range holiday products on the Uzbekistan tourist destination through all key distribution channels. We will harness the power of word of mouth and increase Uzbekistan's presence across all online and key social media channels.
Delivery for Uzbekistan	Uzbekistan 2023 offers us a golden opportunity to create stand-out, increase consumer interest levels and position Uzbekistan tourism destination as a "must see" destination next year and beyond.
Increasing sales opportunities	It is needed to increase the number of platforms on offer to industry and trade partners in our target markets to help "close the sale" with potential visitors.
Growing access	We will increase our regional marketing approach and ensure it is aligned with existing access. We will work with co-operatively with carriers to retain strategically important routes and develop new direct air, road access.

The application of a regional approach to the sustainable development of tourism in Uzbekistan, with its synergistic effect, is beneficial not only for Uzbekistan but also for Central Asian countries. The use of regional approaches and cluster approaches in the sustainable development of tourism will allow it to compete with other tourist macro-regions, significantly increase the number of tourists visiting the region through the systematic development of the tourism industry. To do this, there is a need for a unified strategy and centralized institutions, implementing a coordinated Silk Road brand and advertising campaigns "Visit Silk Road" to manage the tourist destination formed on the territory of Central Asia and achieve the set goals.

References:

1. Lesley Pender and Richard Sharpley. The Management of Tourism. London EC1Y 1SP, SAGE Publications Ltd. 372 p.,2005.
2. P.Hayitboyev, U. Matyakubov "ECOLOGICAL TOURISM", (methodical manual) Samarkand – 2010.
3. [Ian Patterson](#).(2020). New Developments in Promoting Tourism in Uzbekistan. [Journal of Tourismology](#) 6(2):1-19
4. Global Data (2019). Strategies for the development of tourism: how it works in the world. Retrieved at: <https://profi.travel/articles/42436/details/uploads/2019/06>. Accessed 16th February, 2022.

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5. CAREC 2030: Connecting the region for joint and sustainable development. Retrieved at: <https://www.adb.org/sites/default/files/institutional/document/388801/carec-2030-ru.pdf> /2017/10/. Accessed 16th February, 2022.
6. Джаббаров И. Г. ГЛАВА 11. ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ ТУРИЗМА УЗБЕКИСТАНА //ББК 60 Н34. – 2021. – С. 159.
7. Djabbarov I. Problems of Organization of Tourist Zones in Free Economic Zones of Bukhara //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). – 2021. – Т. 5. – №. 5.
8. Kayumovich K. O., Gulyamovich D. I., Khudoynazarovich S. A. Information and information technologies in digital tourism //Special issue on financial development perspectives of the life standard in Central Asia April. – 2020. – С. 32.